
Recommendations for Using Data Management Plans in Academic Research Data Management Training

Christian Riedel¹ Axel Wiepke² Boris Jacob³ Niklas Hartmann⁴ Ulrike Lucke⁵

Abstract: In this report, we share our experiences using data management plans (DMP) for the academic teaching of research data management (RDM). We present concepts to train students in a university lecture over a semester and to train researchers in an interdisciplinary collaborative research center in shorter workshop formats. Based on our observations, we provide recommendations for future DMP-based mediations of competencies in handling research data. These recommendations include imparting basic RDM knowledge before building capacities in creating DMPs, establishing feedback loops to evaluate DMPs, and relying on a printed DMP rather than an IT platform when training time is limited.

Keywords: Research Data Management; Data Management Plan; Academic Training

1 Introduction

In recent years, the reproducibility crisis in research has highlighted the importance of effective data management practices to ensure the reliability and transparency of scientific findings that rely on digital data and code [St10, Lo17]. As a result, there has been an increased demand for research data management competencies across all fields of science. The growing adoption of FAIR data principles and the push towards open science has further emphasized the need for better management and sharing of research data [Bo12, Wi16].

To address these challenges, institutions and organizations have begun to promote using data management plans (DMPs) as a tool for training researchers in research data management (RDM) ([Eu18]). DMPs are structured documents that outline how research data will be collected, stored, managed, shared, and preserved throughout the research data life cycle. They have become a common recommendation or requirement for research funding agencies that aim to professionalize and establish standards in research data management. To foster

¹ University of Potsdam, Institute of Computer Science, An der Bahn 2, 14476 Potsdam, Germany, christian.riedel@uni-potsdam.de

² University of Potsdam, Institute of Computer Science, An der Bahn 2, 14476 Potsdam, Germany, wiepke@uni-potsdam.de

³ University of Potsdam, ZIM - Center for Information Technology and Media Management, Am Neuen Palais 10, 14469 Potsdam, Germany, boris.jacob@uni-potsdam.de

⁴ Staats- und Universitätsbibliothek Hamburg Carl von Ossietzky, Von-Melle-Park 3, 20146 Hamburg, Germany, niklas.hartmann@sub.uni-hamburg.de

⁵ University of Potsdam, Institute of Computer Science, An der Bahn 2, 14476 Potsdam, Germany, ulrike.lucke@uni-potsdam.de

this change in the research community, they promote and increasingly require using DMPs as a project and quality management tool in research.

To that end, several institutions and organizations have implemented DMP training programs, including universities, research institutes, libraries, joint projects, and RDM initiatives [Bi18, NPN21, Au22]. These programs aim to provide researchers with the knowledge and skills needed to create effective DMPs that meet the requirements of funding agencies and ensure that research data is properly created, managed, shared, and reused. By doing so, researchers can improve the reliability and transparency of their research, while also complying with the expectations of funding agencies and the broader scientific community. However, despite the long ongoing debate, the overall implementation of research data management activities could be more extensive across multiple scientific disciplines [Co17, Pe20].

This report aims to provide an overview of the experiences of using DMPs for training competencies in research data management based on three training concepts. The concepts involve short and long-term training with mandatory and voluntary participation. We will examine the benefits and challenges of the respective DMP training programs and provide insights into the best practices for implementing such programs based on our experiences. Overall, this report aims to contribute to the ongoing discussion on improving research data management practices and promoting open science in the scientific community.

2 Training Concepts

In this section, we present three different training concepts that we applied to Master students in computer science at the University of Potsdam and researchers in an interdisciplinary Collaborative Research Center (CRC). The Master's students training comprises a research data management course over one semester where students create a sophisticated DMP for their exam. The training aimed at CRC researchers involves creating a DMP for their specific projects. By providing students and researchers with the necessary skills and knowledge to create effective DMPs, these training concepts aim to promote good RDM practices, ensure that research data is managed effectively, and increase the impact and reproducibility of research projects.

2.1 Training Aimed at Students

The curriculum of the summer semester of 2022 contained a module for network-based storage, which we offer regularly. This specific year, we chose an appropriate context of pressing importance: Research Data Management. The course we offered consisted of a lecture and a practice session each week for 14 weeks, and students voluntarily subscribed to it with a payoff of six Credit Points. The course was open for Bachelor and Master students

in computer, educational, and natural sciences. To combine the necessities of the curriculum with the broad field of RDM, we built the following agenda:

1. Foundations of data management
2. Open access, open data and open science
3. Research data management
4. Storage infrastructure and technologies
5. Ethical and legal aspects
6. National and international initiatives

Alongside the theoretical input of the lectures and the practical deepening of knowledge with exercise sheets, we arranged an excursion to the local server infrastructure of the University of Potsdam and invited RDM experts into the course. Prerequisites for admission to the module examination were solving 50% of the exercise sheets and developing a DMP for a project of choice.

In total, eleven students applied for the course, and eight master students of them completed it. The chosen DMP projects were very diverse and involved hypothetical studies they were interested in, a study they or a research group already conducted, and a preparation of a master thesis. During the semester, we presented several IT platforms to help them develop their DMP. All participating students eventually decided to use RDMO⁶.

We used a combined matrix (see table 1) of recommendations of RDMO and learning goals for RDM [Pe22] to evaluate the students' DMPs. The evaluation matrix categories build on the topics addressed during the course. Each category was rated with one point for general information and a second point for further explanation of the given information.

2.2 Training Aimed at Researchers

We conducted two different training concepts designed for researchers in the interdisciplinary CRC 1294 "Data Assimilation". As the CRC incorporates 15 interdisciplinary research projects from mathematics, natural sciences, and related fields, the workshops aim to recognize the diverse needs of researchers across different disciplines, and provide solutions for effectively managing their research data. During this training, participants are introduced to the key concepts and best practices of RDM and are guided through creating a DMP tailored to their specific research project. This involves identifying the project's data management needs and requirements, selecting appropriate data management tools and strategies, and developing a plan for data sharing and preservation.

⁶ <https://rdmo.uni-potsdam.de/>

Category	Explanation
Researchdata-Policies	Relevant Policies of scientific institutions, academic associations, journals and / or funding institutions were addressed.
Ethical Aspects and good scientific practice	Which ethical and legal aspects need to be considered?
Data types and format	Description of the planned data.
	What can the collected data be reused for?
Data protection and personal Data	Do personal data need to be anonymized?
Data security	Who is allowed to access data?
Backups	Are there at least three copies of the data, of which two are in different media and at least one stored externally?
Publication of data	Where will data and findings be published?
Long term storage	Does the plan fit the guidelines regarding archiving the data? Who is responsible for the resources?
Repositories	Which repositories are well suited for the project?
Legal Aspects	Which licenses apply for the data?
Metadata and standards	Which kinds of metadata are levied and do they fit a standard?
Documentation	Where to find further documentation?
Quality	How to ensure data quality in the project?

Tab. 1: Categories for evaluating DMPs

The training programs include a two-hour workshop where participating researchers learn to complete a DMP. The DMP template used in this workshop was created by CRC members in collaboration with the University of Potsdam's research data group and covers aspects of data policies and guidelines, legal and ethical considerations, documentation, and dataset-specific aspects relevant throughout the research data life cycle. In correspondence with these aspects, researchers learn how to classify the research data and code used in their research projects. The classification of these digital artifacts is a crucial component of this workshop. It aims to sensitize participants to the changing requirements of different research data and generate strategies for handling different types of data during their generation, modification, and publication. The DMP Consulting for small research groups involved more individualized training and focused on using a paper and digital version of the CRC-specific DMP on the RDMO platform.

2.2.1 Individual DMP Consulting for Small Research Groups

The individual two-hour consulting session aims to help small research groups in the CRC to fill out or update the CRC-specific DMP. The training is conducted using either a

paper version of the DMP or a digital version of the DMP that is located on the Research Data Management Organiser (RDMO) platform. Unlike the DMP workshop for PhD-level researchers, participants in the consulting session have not received any prior training in research data management. Therefore, the training is designed to be more hands-on and personalized and to provide participants with a more comprehensive understanding of RDM principles and practices.

During the training, participants are guided through creating or updating their DMP. The training is conducted in small groups, which allows for personalized attention and guidance from the trainers. This approach enables participants to develop a deeper understanding of RDM principles and practices and to apply them more effectively to their specific research project, despite not having received any prior RDM training.

2.2.2 DMP Workshop for PhD-level Researchers

The DMP workshop is a mandatory two-hour workshop for PhD-level researchers in the CRC 1294. The workshop intends to provide participants with a more in-depth understanding of RDM and guide them through creating a DMP connected to their research project.

Before attending the workshop, participants have already completed a four-hour RDM workshop a few months earlier, providing them with some basic knowledge of data management. This ensures they have a foundational understanding of RDM principles and are better prepared to engage with the customized DMP workshop.

During the workshop, participants are provided with a paper version of the CRC-specific DMP template that covers all aspects of the interdisciplinary research projects. The workshop begins with an overview of the purpose and importance of a DMP, followed by a discussion of the DMP's key components, such as data collection, storage, sharing, and preservation, and a classification of their research data according to the DMP's components. Participants are then guided through the process of filling out the paper DMP template. At the end of the workshop, participants have completed a DMP, which they can use to guide and update their research data management practices throughout the project's lifecycle. Participants were then asked to share their DMPs for further feedback.

3 Observations

Each of the different training approaches presented unique opportunities and challenges. The most significant ones are summarized below.

Training Aimed at Students

Master students only: The course was open for bachelor and master students alike. The low count of eight students may not represent any reasoning, but it is possible that RDM is

not perceived as relevant at the beginning of the academic career. However, students in the course could position themselves in a subject area, which resulted in lengthy discussions in the exercises.

Projects were found quickly: While preparing the course, we considered making up projects for students that they could elaborate. When asking students to select a project, they all came up with an idea almost instantly. The selected projects were diverse and presented problems similar to those researchers are confronted with. For instance, students expressed concerns such as "I will not generate any data" or "This field is so novel that there are no standards for data or metadata." These concerns were later addressed during the semester.

Same IT platform: During the semester, we presented several templates to aid students in creating a DMP (e.g., DMPTool⁷, RDMO, an example DMP, guidelines from Wiss-Grid⁸ and guiding questions from Horizon 2020⁹) and addressed the according benefits for specific projects. Ultimately, all DMPs were created using RDMO, which might be due to the appropriate usability of the platform or the best fit for all chosen projects. Another possible explanation is that the students used the same platform to simplify assisting one another.

Individual DMP Consulting for Small Research Groups

Knowledge transfer and IT platforms: We noticed that using a digital version of the DMP on the RDMO platform made the training more challenging because participants had to focus on navigating the tool while paying attention to the DMP's content. This observation is consistent with our findings from the DMP workshop for PhD-level researchers.

Group size: The training in small research groups allows for a more individual knowledge transfer compared to the larger group in the DMP workshop. We observed that participants were motivated to ask more specific questions about their research project and received more personalized guidance on shaping their DMP according to their specific needs. This observation suggests that individualized DMP training can be more effective than group training, particularly regarding the individual research data management of participating researchers.

Quality of DMPs: Despite the challenges posed by the digital version of the CRC-specific DMP, we found that the overall quality of the generated DMPs was good. Participants were able to fill out the DMP in a way that was appropriate for their research project, and they were able to identify appropriate data management tools and strategies. This observation suggests that even with a more challenging training environment, participants could still create effective DMPs when individual guidance is provided.

DMP Workshop for PhD-level Researchers

⁷ <https://dmptool.org/>

⁸ https://www.forschungsdaten.org/images/b/b0/Leitfaden_Data-Management-WissGrid.pdf

⁹ https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/gm/reporting/h2020-tpl-oa-data-mgt-plan_en.docx

General understanding: Participants provided positive feedback about the workshop and expressed an overall understanding of the importance of DMPs in research data management. There is a general understanding that DMPs are an excellent tool for including RDM strategies during research. They found the workshop helpful in understanding the critical components of a DMP and identifying appropriate data management tools and strategies regarding their specific research project.

Knowledge transfer and IT platforms: We observed that training DMP competencies over a relatively short workshop is much easier when a printed DMP is used and an additional IT platform such as RDMO is not included in the training. Participants found it straightforward to fill out the paper version of the DMP, as opposed to the digital version that is located on the RDMO platform. This is likely because the printed version is more tangible and easier to handle than the digital version, where navigating through an IT tool that is unknown to most participants causes an additional challenge.

Feedback on the quality of the DMPs: While participants could create DMPs during the workshop, there was minimal follow-up or feedback request on the DMPs that were generated. This means that an actual evaluation of the quality and effectiveness of the DMPs is not possible.

4 Conclusions

Based on our experiences with three distinct training approaches, we identified key conclusions and recommendations for using DMPs as a tool for RDM training.

Firstly, we discovered that prior knowledge of RDM is highly beneficial when teaching DMPs. Participants who had received prior training in RDM could grasp the concepts and apply them to their DMPs more easily. Due to the absence of Bachelor's students in the RDM course, we infer that the perception of the relevance of RDM may increase throughout a researcher's academic career, from undergraduate student to postdoc. From this observation, RDM likely becomes increasingly relevant to everyday research as researchers gain more work experience. Therefore, we recommend addressing RDM early and throughout a researcher's academic career to reinforce and build upon their prior knowledge and to establish feedback routines to evaluate RDM strategies continuously.

Secondly, we found that DMPs serve as an excellent tool to expand, apply and evaluate RDM knowledge. By requiring participants to create a DMP, they have to think critically about their research data and the strategies they will use throughout the research process. DMPs also include various RDM components to assess the students' competencies. Working on DMPs can strengthen and build upon their prior RDM knowledge.

However, we also noted that training in IT platforms for DMP generation could be more effective when participants have existing RDM knowledge. Although IT platforms can be helpful, they may pose additional challenges for those unfamiliar with RDM. Thus,

we recommend using a printed version of the DMP for training when time is limited and participants need to gain prior knowledge on an IT platform for DMP generation. Nonetheless, it is still advisable to allocate sufficient time to work on DMPs and provide regular individual support in small groups when planning RDM training sessions.

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